

SECTION: IT MANAGEMENT

SMART CITY: AN OVERVIEW OF THE FUNCTIONS OF CITY MARKETING MOBILE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT: The marketing activities of cities increasingly rely on information providing applications available for smartphones, which supplement and support the information system of cities and its use. Our study aims to explore and identify application functions accessible for mobile phones that are the most essential for consumers, and to make proposals on how to optimise functions available in applications by adjusting them to consumers' needs. Customizing of applications (e.g. local governments, destination managers) are always grappling with a shortage of resources, which is a problem that the measures outlined in this study for defining optimal functions for mobile applications offer an effective solution to, thereby helping to enrich and update contents made available to locals and tourists, and to improve the quality of online services and those available on smart phones. The basic assumption of our study was that different generations of consumers manifest different consumer behaviours in this field, and therefore we analysed data from our primary research with this in mind. We introduce our results in a breakdown by generations and functions.

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1. Introduction

The aim of the study is to arrive at practicable proposals for technology developments. We considered it a key objective during our research to define the main elements and features of a marketable software solution (mobile application platform), which may work with most city marketing applications based on mobile technologies. This could enable the creation of a scheme or engine on which applications are based, and which could meet the demands of several municipalities at the same time. This could help reduce the development costs of local governments during their cooperation with other tourism organisations and institutions as several actors could benefit from the same application or its platform.

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The analysis of consumers' needs and their behavioural process in relation to the mobile application can be performed based on two groups. While city marketing applications are targeted at the local residents of cities and also tourists, destination marketing is only targeted at tourists. We focused on the residents of cities in our research. We assumed that different consumer generations will have preference for different functions, which our analysis also extends to. In our identification of the problems, we formulated several research questions, to which we sought replies by way of an online questionnaire survey.

1. Are consumers aware of city marketing mobile phone applications available where they live?
2. Do consumers use such applications?
3. What functions would they want to use and with what priorities in a city marketing application?

2. Explanation of the conceptual framework of the research

2.1. Links between city marketing and destination marketing and their importance

City marketing as an independent and important area of marketing has been gaining significance since the 1970s and 1980s. This was the time when changes occurred that encouraged cities to use marketing tools. Industrial activities started to lose ground in big cities, while the share of the third sector, i.e. services started to grow. The start of the globalization process - which brought with it the competition for tourists and investors - is also linked to that period. It is not only countries, but also cities and regions that are in a fight to attract entrepreneurs, residents, tourists and investors, and to convince them about why it is worth choosing their city.

The role of cities also changed with globalization and the transformation of needs: leisure time, and searching for cultural and entertainment opportunities received more attention, and it became important what advantages a city can offer short-term (for tourists) and long-term (for residents of the city or area) for the improvement of the quality of life.

The changes described above moved local governments towards adopting a marketing approach and using marketing tools. In city marketing, we can consider local governments to be local organisational forces and the creators of the whole system (Boros-Garamhegyi, 2009; László, 1998; Piskóti, 2012).

As the above suggests, city marketing is a very wide area. The market, the group of consumers is complex, and the competition takes place at several different levels: a municipality may be competing for residents, investors, resources (applications, EU funds) and also for tourists.

Competition is particularly fierce now in the computerized world, as tourists compare and decide which city will be their destination based on previously available information.

The concept of city identity is closely linked to city marketing. Its aim is to communicate comparative advantages to the targeted segments in a clearly understandable way. Szabó (2011) highlights three elements in relation to city identity:

- *City design* (geographical features, architectural image, self-depiction - i.e. flag, coat of arms, typography in publications),
- *City culture* (traditions, customs, or even the life philosophy or lifestyle of the residents),
- *City communication* (which may take the form of different events or written materials, leaflets).

Mobile applications and integrated digital information systems are obvious parts of city communication in today's computerized world. City design can be an integral part of the visual realization of mobile applications. The contents of the application are partly also determined by city culture.

FIGURE 1. LINKS BETWEEN CITY MARKETING, IT MANAGEMENT AND TOURISM

Source: Diagram constructed by the authors.

The main area of city marketing is not tourism, but an appropriate strategy for the whole city's management and communication, the aim of which is to increase local well-being. One part of this is made up by coordinated marketing activities, which have evolved into a separate branch of marketing. In tourism terms, a destination is a city, municipality or geographical region, i.e. a destination with appropriate coordinated services that tourists may choose. According to the definition of Piskóti (2014, p. 8.): "Destination marketing is a specialized sub-area of municipality marketing, which may contribute to achieving the municipality's goals by increasing the competitiveness of tourism in the market."¹

¹ Original text: "A desztináció-marketing a településmarketing része, sajátos szakmaterületi síkja, mely a turisztikai piaci versenyképesség növelésével tud hozzájárulni a településcélok eléréséhez" (Piskóti, 2014, p. 8.).

Figure 1 below contains a chart highlighting the links between specialized areas of marketing, IT management and tourism. The mobile applications discussed in detail in this study are a cross-section of the three disciplines depicted in the chart.

2.2. Smartphone technologies for potential use in city marketing

Several different IT solutions are used in city marketing, some of the most often used of which we are discussing below.

- Phone calls - such as calling destinations directly
- Wi-Fi connection - for downloading data
- Audio play - for guided walks
- Bluetooth connection - for downloading data
- Camera recordings - e.g. for reading QR-codes or for augmented reality
- NFC sensing and connection - for data transfer similar to QR codes
- Push notification - e.g. notifications about different events
- Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) - such as links to Google Maps or different social media websites
- RSS Feeds - e.g. for downloading and displaying news and articles of resources

We researched existing Hungarian city marketing solutions for our assessment of the technological opportunities, and also conducted interviews with the creators of several software solutions (Iványi, 2014), which enabled us to learn about their goals and already implemented solutions.

TABLE 1. COMPARISON OF ALREADY IMPLEMENTED FUNCTIONS

Local sights	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Tours																		+
Local government information	+		+		+		+	+	+									+
Local shops, services	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+										+
Discounts	+		+		+													+
Events	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+										+
News																		+
Error reporting	+																	+
Maps	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+							+
Mobile parking	+																	+

Source: Table constructed by the authors.

As a fundamental observation, we can say that several districts of Budapest have their own application introducing the area, and we also found examples for mobile applications in other larger cities. We discuss a selection of the most characteristic city marketing or destination marketing applications available for Android smart phones on Google Play (the offer on Apple Store for iOS devices such as iPhone or iPad is the same with only a few exceptions). We present the major features of applications as part of our discussion of their different functions in Table 1.

2.3. Identifying consumer generations for the purpose of mobile applications

There are several methods for grouping consumers into generations based on their characteristics. In this study, we rely on the work of Oblinger & Oblinger (2005) in our distinction of generations X, Y and Z.

- Generation X: consumers born between 1965 and 1980
- Generation Y: consumers born between 1981 and 1995
- Generation Z: consumers born between 1995 and today

Generation Y is also called the IT generation because they have a slightly different attitude towards technology. Generation Y and Z feels that technological devices are their friends and can help them to find any solution or answer. For generation X it is getting harder and harder to understand and learn how the up-to-date mobile and smartphone technologies work (Szijártó, 2014).

3. Results of the quantitative survey

During our online survey between 01/06/2017 and 15/06/2017, 110 respondents filled in our questionnaire in the LimeSurvey questionnaire editing and data collection system, which we announced in several Facebook groups, or asked friends on Facebook to spread it on a voluntary basis, relying on a snowball effect.

The age distribution of the sample is shown in Figure 2.

FIGURE 2. AGE DISTRIBUTION OF THE SAMPLE

Source: Own elaboration.

The snowball effect and voluntary online participation gave us an opportunity to actually receive responses only from those who take a real interest in the topic, but this also renders the sample significantly less representative (Malhotra, 2009). Based on theoretical research

on consumer behaviour (Hofmeister-Tóth, 2014; Tari, 2010; Törőcsik, 2011) we assumed that there is a difference between the behaviour and preferences of the generations determined based on their birth year, especially as regards their use and acceptance of devices - smart phones and the applications for these. We weighted the responses in accordance with Hungarian data on these generations, by which we attempted to offset the over-representation of the Z generation. Table 2 shows data from the 2011 survey of Hungary's Central Statistics Office for each generation.

TABLE 2. CORRECTION FIGURES PER GENERATIONS

X GENERATION	Y GENERATION	Z GENERATION	
1654885	2361095	1674951	Total population in 2011
0.290793369	0.414887301	0.29431933	Share of the three generations out of the total population
0.056074766	0.38317757	0.560747664	Share out of the sample
5.185815086	1.082754662	0.524869472	Multiplication factor

Source: Table constructed by the authors.

The Y generation was slightly under-represented in the sample (its multiplication factor is 1.08), while the Z generation was significantly over-represented (multiplication factor 0.524), for which reason it was not necessary to use a high multiplication factor in such cases, as the variation of the accuracy of the data did not increase significantly, i.e. we consider the results to be reliable, and the results after correction to be relevant. As a result of the significant under-representation of the X generation and also the resulting high correction factor (multiplication factor 5.18) the conclusions deduced in relation to them show a very high variation, for which reason we do not consider them to be relevant. The total sample size is appropriate for us to deduce conclusions for all three generations based on the results corrected using the correction factors. The results below are based on figures corrected using the correction factors. With all our calculations, we also calculated values without correction, and examined the difference of the two figures. We will highlight more significant differences below in our textual explanations.

The questionnaire is divided into 4 main blocks:

Block I. The focus in the first block was on identifying the respondents' place of residence and whether they own smart devices. On the one hand, the respondent had to own at least a smart phone or a tablet as a smart device for them to be able to reply to questions concerning the functions of applications. On the other hand, we identified for each respondent based on where they live whether there is a local mobile application solution (operated by the local government, non-profit, or operated by an external company for-profit) available at their place of residence.

Block II. Questions on awareness of currently available city marketing applications were grouped in a separate block, which we linked to the place of residence as described under Block I. We extended the analysis by one further dimension by doing so.

Block III. and Block IV. We used two consecutive blocks to determine the optimal functions of city marketing mobile applications. In the first block, respondents had to reply to a

multiple choice question and choose at least 4, but no more than 8 functions important for them out of altogether 15 functions already implemented in existing applications. The second block was then based on the replies to this multiple choice question and asked the respondents to rank the selected 4 to 8 functions in order of priority. These interlinked blocks have a twofold significance:

- a. The consumer can select items more easily from a longer list of functions without making a particularly great effort to compare these.
- b. The consumer has to rate items from a more transparent and more manageable list, which means that we can have rankings without asking a greater effort of the respondents.

Based on the results of Block I, Figure 3 below shows the occurrence of more important electronic devices in the sample.

FIGURE 3. OCCURRENCE OF ELECTRONIC DEVICES IN THE SAMPLE

Source: Own elaboration.

FIGURE 4. VARIATION OF THE SAMPLE BY BUDAPEST'S DISTRICTS

Source: Own elaboration.

Based on the results of the second focus of Block I, 62% of respondents said they were from Budapest, while the variations of the districts within Budapest are shown in Figure 4.

Based on the districts and municipalities identified, we assigned the information to every respondent as to whether an Android or iOS application exists for their place of residence. Those who indicated that they have a smart phone or tablet also had to answer a question on the operating system running on their smart device according to their knowledge (Android, iOS, Windows or other). Figures 5 and 6 below show the distribution of answers between Android, iOS and Windows smart phones and tablets. While the sample clearly shows a much more significant representation of Android among smart phones, the competition between iOS and Android seems to be much more balanced as regards tablets.

FIGURE 5. DISTRIBUTION OF THE OPERATION SYSTEMS OF MOBILE PHONES

Source: Own elaboration.

FIGURE 6. DISTRIBUTION OF THE OPERATION SYSTEMS OF TABLETS

Source: Own elaboration.

If local governments intend to develop applications for mobile phones, those for Android should definitely be given priority. This decision is particularly important in cases where the available financial resources are very limited.

We divided our questions in Block II on mobile application solutions already existing at the respondents' place of residence into two groups. In one group, users are certain that there is a city marketing mobile application where they live, while in the other group they only assume that one exists. We considered this distinction to be important as it allowed us to identify the group of informed users (those who are well-informed and confirm that they know whether such an application exists or not) and non-informed users (those who are not sure about this information, yet tried to answer the question). The results from aggregating the replies are shown in Figures 7 and 8.

FIGURE 7. CERTAINTY OF INFORMEDNESS OF USERS CONCERNING THE EXISTENCE OF APPLICATIONS

Source: Own elaboration.

FIGURE 8. THE CORRECTNESS OF USERS' INFORMATION ON APPLICATION

Source: Own elaboration.

It is apparent that most respondents are not certain about their answers, but assume that such an application exists; only the local administration probably does not communicate the fact properly. Based on applications available so far and the analysis of the communication of municipal governments related to these we can establish that local governments do not place sufficient emphasis on ensuring that information on the applications is communicated to locals. The ratio of correct answers is significantly higher among those who are certain, but even there it happens that the answer given in relation to existence of a mobile application is not the correct one. Altogether more than 70% of the respondents answered the question correctly as to whether there is a mobile application available for the place of their residence, even though the great majority of them only guessed.

In Block III and Block IV, the respondents had to determine functions necessary for an ideal application. The 15 items on the list of functions are based on all known currently available city marketing applications in Hungary. In the first step, respondents had to select 4 to 8 functions from the list that they considered the most important or necessary, and in the second step rank these in order of preference.

The second column of Table 3 shows the ratio of respondents out of the sample who selected the individual functions. It is clear that information about local events, services and shops is important to almost everybody, followed by a map, support for administrative activities, local government information and mobile parking.

TABLE 3. DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE GENERATIONS IN THE SELECTION OF FUNCTIONS

	RATIO OF SELECTION X GENERATION Y GENERATION Z GENERATION			
Local events	90%	100%	90%	88%
List of local services, shops	71%	67%	76%	77%
Local sights	68%	67%	76%	65%
Maps	63%	67%	59%	72%
Electronic helpdesk, administration	59%	50%	68%	62%
Local government information	58%	50%	63%	65%
Mobile parking	57%	83%	56%	38%
Fault reporting (e.g. public lighting, pot-holes)	56%	50%	63%	58%
News	53%	67%	44%	58%
Local discounts	38%	50%	39%	28%
Walks	21%	17%	22%	27%
Special offers of local shops	15%	17%	12%	20%
Forum, chatting option	12%	17%	15%	5%
Local video and image gallery	9%	17%	2%	10%
Games	2%	0%	2%	5%

Source: Table constructed by the authors.

While local events, local services, shops, maps and mobile parking are also available in other applications (such as Google Maps or the Events Calendar of Facebook), electronic helpdesks and local government information are not available in other applications.

Table 4 shows the average ranking of functions. The difference here is that maps, local shops, services and mobile parking ranked much lower, i.e. even though they were selected by many respondents, they were not prioritised as much, because these services are also

available in other applications. It is interesting, however, that local events are also at the top of the list here. Even though these are available on other platforms, they are becoming increasingly important due to event tourism and the search for excitement. Festivals for example are increasingly a part of our lives, whether we want to spend our leisure time where we live, or take a trip to another city.

TABLE 4. AVERAGE RANKINGS OF FUNCTIONS BASED
ON THE RESULTS OF THE PRIORITISED LISTS

LOCAL EVENTS	3.39
News	3.47
Electronic helpdesk, administration	3.54
Fault reporting (e.g. public lighting, pot-holes)	3.67
List of local services, shops	3.78
Local government information	3.94
Local sights	3.98
Walks	4.11
Special offers of local shops	4.18
Local discounts	4.40
Maps	4.62
Forum, chatting option	5.29
Games	5.36
Mobile parking	5.68
Local video and image gallery	7.67

Source: Table constructed by the authors.

Columns 3 to 5 of Table 4 show the average rankings for each generation (with occasional ties). It can be established that while events and sights are much more important for the Z generation, walks, local government information, offers of local shops or fault reporting and helpdesk services are increasingly prioritised by the Y and X generation.

TABLE 5. RANKING OF FUNCTIONS IN THE BREAKDOWN BY GENERATIONS

	GEN. Z	GEN. Y	GEN. X
Local events	1	3	5
Local sights	2	9	8
News	3	5	4
List of local services, shops	4	4	8
Electronic helpdesk, administration	5	2	6
Maps	6	7	12
Fault reporting (e.g. public lighting, pot-holes)	7	10	1
Local government information	8	6	6
Local discounts	9	8	10
Walks	10	11	1
Forum, chatting option	11	14	11
Special offers of local shops	12	13	1
Mobile parking	13	12	13
Local video and image gallery	14	15	14
Games	15	1	15

Source: Table constructed by the authors.

As we launched our research, we assumed that different generations will present different consumer behaviours. Table 5 shows the ratios of opinions within the single generations as compared to the ratio within the entire sample. Differences can be observed, but after performing two-sample proportion tests also taking the size of the sample in consideration we found that there is no difference between these assuming a significance level of 5%, and therefore differences between the generations cannot be interpreted.

Our analysis also extended to establishing rankings based on functions selected as 1st, 1st to 2nd, 1st to 3rd and 1st to 4th by respondents. Rankings do not change significantly and are close to the aggregated rankings after the first three positions despite the fact that 4 to 8 functions could be selected, and on average more than six functions had to be ranked. Table 6 enables a comparison of all rankings.

TABLE 6. RANKINGS OF INDIVIDUAL FUNCTIONS BASED ON THEIR POSITION IN THE PRIORITISED LISTS

RANKINGS	POSITION 1	POSITION 1 TO 2	POSITION 1 TO 3	POSITION 1 TO 4	AGGREGATED RANKINGS	RATE OF SELECTION
Local events	4	1	1	1	1	1
List of local services, shops	8	7	2	2	5	2
Electronic helpdesk, administration	2	2	3	3	3	5
News	7	3	4	4	2	9
Local sights	1	4	5	5	7	3
Local government information	5	5	7	6	6	6
Fault reporting (e.g. public lighting, pot-holes)	3	6	6	7	4	8
Maps	6	8	8	8	11	4
Local discounts	10	11	9	9	10	10
Walks	11	9	10	10	8	11
Mobile parking	9	12	11	11	14	7
Special offers of local shops	12	10	12	12	9	12
Forum, chatting option	13	14	14	13	12	13
Games	13	13	13	14	13	15
Local video and image gallery	13	14	15	15	15	14

Source: Table constructed by the authors.

It is frequently a problem that local governments only have resources for the development of a few functions. It is therefore particularly important what functions place first, and what combinations of these are the most common. Table 7 below shows the 5 most frequent functions from Positions 1 and 2 of the rankings (see Table 6, Column 3). Based on these results we can establish that the most common pair of functions in Positions 1 and 2 are electronic helpdesk and local government information, and local events in combination with local sights also occur frequently. We can therefore conclude that the two most important areas for development for local governments are e-government and e-helpdesk, up-to-date news, and introducing events and sights in the form of a mobile application.

TABLE 7. THE MOST COMMON COMBINATIONS OF FUNCTIONS
 IN POSITION 1 TO 2 OF THE RANKINGS

Local sights	Local government information	Electronic helpdesk, administration	Local events	News	
-	2		10	1	Local sights
	-	10	3	1	Local government information
		-	3	2	Electronic helpdesk, administration
			-	7	Local events
				-	News

Source: Table constructed by the authors.

4. Conclusion

The main focus of our research was the definition of an optimal set of functions for mobile applications, which may be of help for the planning of city development and communication activities. We can argue based on our results that local governments do not place appropriate emphasis on ensuring that information on existing mobile applications is received by local residents.

We wish to summarise our main findings as follows.

- In terms of operating systems available on smart phones, Android-based technological developments should be prioritised. This decision is particularly important in cases where the available financial resources are very limited.
- The two most important areas for development for local governments are e-government and e-helpdesk on the one hand, and up-to-date news introducing events and sights in the form of a mobile application on the other.

Our basic assumption that different generations of consumers will present different consumer behaviours was not confirmed. Differences between the individual generations in terms of the use of mobile applications could not be interpreted based on the sample used.

As a further avenue for research it would be worth conducting in-depth interviews with application developers which could contribute to a further optimisation of city marketing mobile application toolkits.

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